

Multilateralism in Crisis?

Assessing the impact of COVAX in Africa

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Introduction

The emergence of the new coronavirus disease (COVID-19) led to a high index of mortality worldwide and continues threatening to push an additional 150 million people into extreme poverty by the end of 2021 (World Bank, 2020). This experience was strongly supported by the unavailability of COVID-19 vaccines because while these provide a light at the end of the pandemic tunnel, they illuminate glaring inequalities between and within nations in terms of access to vaccines, health systems to administer them, infrastructure to store and transport them, as well as revealing issues of transparency in their distribution along with misinformation.

The World Bank (2021) asserts that National access to effective vaccines against COVID-19 is being decided by a country's financial and diplomatic clout rather than its actual health needs. This is according to leading academics and officials from Africa, Asia, the Caribbean and South America. They note that this is because the planet has been divided between the rich North with rapid mass access to the vaccine and the Global South without. The World Bank (2021) further submits that in response to this global division, a completely new mindset is required to address the political issue of producing and distributing vaccines against COVID -19 in a fair, affordable way, that is one that views the virus and its impacts as more than just another disease and sees the pandemic for what it is, "a global crisis in a globalized world."

Currently, COVID-19 vaccinations have been deployed and are available in several countries. There must however be efforts to combat vaccine hesitancy (VH) COVID-19, particularly in Africa as a continent in which vaccine hesitancy has already been recorded after new vaccines have been introduced. Therefore, this paper will explain the role of Multilateralism in the fight against COVID-19 in the African continent by emphasizing the vaccine distribution, access, vaccine hesitancy and other relevant developments in the region. In terms of structure, this paper will first provide a theoretical framework that explains the African case regarding vaccine distribution, highlighting the role of Multilateralism. Furthermore, it will explain the role of Multilateralism in the fight against COVID-19, discuss COVID-19 Vaccine Global Access (COVAX) in Africa. Challenges and alternatives will be provided according to the information previously discussed. The findings and analysis will be summarized in the conclusion.

Theoretical Framework

Multilateralism and global cooperation is in a constant state of transformation that reflects the power dynamics at the global level. Hence, in a multipolar world, the Multilateral system has also been diversified into different poles. The typical United Nations Multilateralism has seen itself affected by the rising problems coming from global inequalities, climate change and increasing political polarization. Therefore, academics and politicians have expressed their concern about the decline of United Nations center Multilateralism (Da Silva Gama, 2021; Oshiba, 2021). Nonetheless, the world reaction to the COVID 19 pandemic has demonstrated that multilateralism has not declined. Instead, it has mutated into regional multilateralism or serves as a platform for bilateralism multiple (Lavallée, 2021; Bellis et al., 2018).

The need for cooperation and stability has been one of the core pillars in the creation of multilateralism. In this view, a crisis can serve as the momentum for fragmentation or a catalyzer for a stronger multilateral system. Significantly, the view rooted in the liberal theory seems to be more effective when a crisis cannot be attributed to an actor, and when the consequences have a global reach. Climate change was a sign of this dynamic (Terhalle & Depledge, 2013) and now the COVID-19 pandemic exposed the thereof assumption. Yet, the reality is far more complex. Evidently, the World Health Organization (WHO) became a platform for coordinating a response to the crisis. However, scientific research remained divided into blocks and vaccine distribution divided by the Global North-South line (Sachs, 2020).

Moreover, cooperation had continued by the COVAX mechanism and by other forms through Regional Institutions and bilateral cooperation, such as the involvement of the African Union and the European Union as coordinators to close the dysfunction in global cooperation (Lavallée, 2021). In doing so, the Regional Institutions have undertaken a crucial role while at the same time they have also become hubs for United Nations Multilateral cooperation. In the case of Africa, the African Union served to distribute a portion of the donation of vaccine coming from China, which was oriented to its bilateral allies in Africa (Bridge Consulting, 2021).

In the case study, the research demonstrates the impact of COVAX in the African continent while empathizing with it the role of the African Union as a multilateral entity working to complement the United Nations centric multilateralism. In doing so, the case study challenges the traditional conceptualization to Western dominated multilateralism by exposing multi-level cooperation and the effectiveness of a more decentralized multilateral system.

COVID-19 and Multilateralism

The fight for COVID-19 resistance has led to severe vaccine nationalism and has hindered global support in the production, purchase and distribution of vaccines and it is very unfortunate that the battle to develop digital vaccine certificates has started down the same path (Nache et al, 2021). According to the European Commission (2021), thirteen vaccines have been approved in different countries and 23 more candidates are undertaking trials for effectiveness. The European Commission further says they are faced with a multitude of national and regional regulatory agencies differentially giving approval to a plethora of vaccines valid.

Nache et al (2021) however submit that a vaccine certificate valid for cross-border travel is thus likely to bring chaos and misperception if it does not go hand in hand with global support as numerous diverse messages from public administration, private corporations and the media will only compound disorder. For example, China's vaccine certificate is only valid for Chinese vaccines and also European Union's certificate would include the four vaccines approved by the European Medicine Agency (EMA), Pfizer-BioNTech, Moderna, Astrazeneca/University of Oxford and Jansen.

World Health Organization (2021) states that Individual European Countries such as Hungary or Slovakia which have added non-EMA accepted vaccines including Sputnik V and Sinopharm to their arsenal would include these in their certificates, whereas Greece and Israel have already made arrangements to permit their people to move freely between their countries. The situation becomes even more complex if the International Air Transport Associations and groups of airlines create their own systems beside those of national governments.

According to the Airports Council International (2021), the international Civil Aviation Organization has called for coordination of global standards and the WHO has established a Smart Certificate Working group to figure out how to normalize and integrate all of the diverse vaccines accepted in individual countries of the world, Vaccines certificates can only be successful if there is global cooperation.

The United Nations Security Council (2021) postulates that the Security Council on the 26th of February announced the adoption of a resolution calling for strengthened international cooperation to facilitate equitable and affordable access to COVID-19 vaccines in armed conflict and post conflict situations as well as during complex humanitarian emergencies. Acting through its special silence procedure enacted during the pandemic, the Council unanimously adopted resolution 2565 (2021), recognizing the role of extensive immunization against COVID-19 as a global public good for health. It stressed the need to develop international partnerships, particularly capabilities, in recognition of differing national contexts.

Furthermore, the council requested the Secretary General to provide a full assessment of the impediments to vaccine accessibility and the COVID-19 response, including vaccination programmes in situations of armed conflict and complex humanitarian emergencies as necessary and also make recommendations to the Council. The Security Council expressed its intention to review situations brought to its attention by the Secretary-General where hostilities and armed group activities are impeding COVID-19 vaccination and to consider what further measures may be necessary to ensure such impediments are removed, and hostilities paused to enable vaccination (United Nations Security Council, 2021).

Divides between High and Low Income Countries

According to Paterson (2021), the 100 day challenge which ended on 7 April was launched in January to close the gap in vaccine accessibility between high-and low-income countries. Meanwhile, it was unlikely that any governments in the world could have at least begun to vaccinate their homes within 100 days from the beginning of the year, said Dr Richard Mihigo, the coordinator of the Regional Office for Africa's International Immunization and Disease Prevention Body Programs. However, as the deadline approached, 36 countries were covered by COVAX, the WHO's Initiative to provide global access to vaccines against the coronavirus have not yet embarked on national vaccination programs. Of these, the majority (26) are lower middle income or low-income countries.

Paterson (2021) further mentions that in Africa, vaccination programmes only started from the end of February, in Ghana about two months after they started being rolled out in wealthier parts of the world. Of the 536 million vaccine doses that had been injected worldwide at the end of March, 76% were delivered in 10 High Income Countries, including the United States, and only 27 million in Africa about 5% of the total. This evidently shows that the 100-day campaign which according to Roberto Lopez, who leads *Acción Internacional para la Salud*, a South American network of organisations seeking universal access to crucial medicines represented an international cry for help on the part of the WHO, had fallen on deaf ears. Indeed, the economic dependence on wealthier countries among the world's poorer states was described as a significant factor potentially inhibiting Middle and Low-Income Countries from accessing vaccines.

Despite widespread acknowledgement that viruses do not respect borders, India's devastating experience with COVID-19 calls into question the degree to which the International community is willing to translate ideas into practice. Programs like the COVID-19 Vaccine Global Access (COVAX) are supposed to ensure a more equitable distribution of Covid19 vaccines, but the reality seems instead to reinforce the inequalities around vaccine distribution. While shipments of the AstraZeneca vaccine from the United States will be helpful, there is more that it could do to ameliorate the shortages in India and the inequitable access to COVID vaccines more generally (East Asia Forum, 2021).

The East Asia Forum (2021) postulates that a program like COVAX or donations from the United States can only do so much to resolve structural inequalities that limit access to pharmaceuticals and vaccines as it addresses the immediate issues but not the underlying root causes that give rise to maldistribution in the first place. If world leaders want to make pharmaceuticals more accessible, they need to change the intellectual property system governing therapeutic drugs.

Youde (2021) however states that intellectual property rights grant creators the right to control who gets to produce and under what conditions through the granting of patents. This control is supposed to reward innovation by allowing creators of intellectual property to reap the rewards from their discoveries. The outbreak in India shows what happens when that collaboration is absent or slow in coming. Thus, the action needed requires a willingness to change the rules about pharmaceutical intellectual property rights to match the scope and scale of the challenge from the disease that the global community faces (East Asian Forum, 2021).

According to the United Nations Human Rights Council (2021), unfortunately this has not been the case in almost all the Global South States in which close to 90 % of the world's population lives. The world therefore faces a sharp and highly problematic vaccine-divide in which the much richer Global North States, which host a very small percentage of the global population, have so far concerned the vast majority of available COVID-19 vaccines, leaving the bulk of the world's population with almost no access to these medicines.

High Income countries have understandably acted according to their perceived national self-interest and under great political pressure from their own populations to rapidly end the pandemic for them. They believe that the pandemic will end for them once their populations receive these vaccines, regardless of whether the same experience is simultaneously replicated in the Low-Income countries that host most of the world's population (UN HRC, 2021). In this sense, the United Nations Security Council (2021) emphasized the urgent need for solidarity, equity and efficacy," inviting donation of vaccine doses from developed economies and all those in position to do so for low and middle-income countries and other countries in need,

particularly through COVAX. Similarly, to facilitate a global mechanism for pooled procurement and equitable distribution of COVID-19 vaccine.

COVAX in Africa

Nachege et al, (2021) notes that continuous debate and worry is being held in Low and Medium Income compared to high-income nations about accessing COVID-19 vaccines and roll-out gaps. Many African countries which have poor revenue, have reciprocity problems in their populations following the vaccination trials as they need to transfer vaccine production domestically. In order to convey exact information and facilitate optimum vaccine uptake, effective health communication and intense community involvement is NEEDED. In this light, national governments are addressing their problems quickly with the help of partners such as WHO and Africa Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. The African Vaccination Acquisition Team of the African Union and the COVAX collaboration, directed by the WHO, with worldwide partners aim to attain a 60% COVID-19 vaccine capability for 720 million doses by June 2022. This effort offers chances for future international co-operation to enhance equitable implementation in disadvantaged countries of COVID-19 vaccinations. As of March 4, 2021, 11 countries have begun vaccination programs across Africa. The Oxford University and AstraZeneca Vaccine have received COVAX doses among them, Ghana, Nigeria, Kenya, Angola, Côte d'Ivoire and the Democratic Republic of Congo under the COVAX program.

According to Nkengasong et al (2020), the grand experiment which was initiated in order to accelerate the development of COVID-19 vaccines and ensure that they are distributed evenly among higher- and lower-income nations. The COVID-19 Vaccine Global Access (COVAX) Initiative is a welcome endeavor. The WHO, Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI), and Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance are co-leaders. As of October 1st, 167 countries had signed up, accounting for roughly two-thirds of the world's population. Gavi (2020) however states that more people have shown interest. The effort covers a number of vaccinations that are currently being tested and it is vital to ensure that whichever ones show to be effective are available. Gavi (2020) further says even poor countries should have enough vaccines to safeguard healthcare personnel and the most vulnerable 20% of their people under this plan. Africa, though, has reason to be concerned. Several high-income countries have already inked contracts with certain businesses to purchase specific vaccines. The United States, for example, has struck deals for up to US\$6 billion with a number of companies. According to Oxfam, even if all five of the most advanced vaccine options are successful, there will not be enough vaccines for the majority of the world's inhabitants until 2022 (Nkengasong et al, 2020).

Accordingly, for the Sub-Saharan Africans access to vaccinations, treatments and COVID-19 diagnosis will be a challenge. It is important to work with vaccine developers, procure COVID-19 therapeutic products and local test and diagnostic materials. A fundamental difficulty for countries in Sub-Saharan Africa will be access to effective COVID-19 therapies, since therapeutic manufacture often focuses on profitable Western markets and is poorly matched to the realities of sub-Saharan Africa. The Africa Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, in conjunction with the African Union, are able to profit from combined COVID-19 therapy procurement. The COVID-19 pandemic should be a wake-up call for sub-Saharan Africa to develop vaccinations, therapy and diagnostic capabilities to meet public health emergencies (Bright et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the use of a COVID-19 vaccination would help combat the disease. It would not be conceivable without providing vaccines for all regions of the world with their availability,

accessibility and affordability. With regard to the possible availability to the use of vaccines and the need for Africa as a continent, there remains the appropriate question: who will pay for Africa? In the past, African countries had an injustice with antiretroviral drugs, which in the past has led to the deaths of millions of Africans. The history has justified the African countries' worry over what COVID-19 vaccinations offer. If certain actions and aid are not undertaken for the continent, the burden of disease for Africa will last longer than expected (Lucero-Prisno et al. 2021).

Currently, despite limited resources in the continent, the response to coronavirus disease (COVID-19) has been rapid, forward-thinking and adaptive in many African countries. The continued growth of cases and deaths which required rapid development of an effective vaccination have led to these reactions. It is hoped that more transparency will be exercised and evidence-based methods will be provided by African Governments and public health professionals to support COVID-19 vaccines and develop fair and effective population vaccine programmes. This analysis evaluated Africa's readiness and responsiveness to vaccinations under COVID-19, possible demand, acceptability and distribution problems associated with viral management. The study examines the readiness and distribution of the vaccines in context, as well as the need for vaccines and the related problems. The report provides innovative ways and techniques to optimize the benefits of COVID-19 virus overcoming vaccinations in African countries. This would include the implementation of vaccinations that can contribute to the concession of immunity or protection against the virus in the setting of certain African countries, such as socio-cultural and economic factors (Hagan et al, 2021).

During a debate on vaccination trials on French television in early April 2020, a top French clinician advised that a vaccine study assessing the efficacy of a decades-old tuberculosis vaccine, bacille Calmette-Guérin (BCG), against COVID-19 be done in Africa. WHO Director General, who is African, was strong in his response to the ensuing debate. The Director General of the WHO condemned the remarks, calling them "appalling, shameful, and racist," and stated, "Africa cannot and will not be a trial ground for any [COVID-19] vaccine." Furthermore, "the residue from a colonial mentality must end." The Director General has said that Africa will not host vaccine tests of COVID-19 in reply to provocative comments of the two European clinicians and scientists. Such a posture could stigmatize COVID-19 in Africa and take away crucial research from Africa. On the contrary, Africa must host COVID-19 vaccination studies for public health, science and ethics (Singh ,2020).

In Africa, while images of the COVID 19 vaccination in nations with great income verify inequalities in global health, the vaccines which are promising and largely unreliable still have a long delay. However, the global COVAX initiative to enable quick and fair access of all countries to COVID-19 vaccination, irrespective of income level, has been adopted for African countries. By the end of 2021, 20% of its population will be provided with vaccines via COVAX, however, this is insufficient for the continent, which aims at vaccinating at least 60% of the population of this continent. So, even though Africa is behind the rest of the globe in implementing COVID 19 vaccinations, receiving them around a year after WHO's emergency clearance is an unparalleled feat that shows that age long medication lags are decreasing (Rockville, MD, USA). Besides the continent's vaccine doses via COVAX, Africa alone has obtained 250 million further doses through the African Vaccine Acquisition Task Team from Pfizer, AstraZeneca and Johnson & Johnson. On January 13, 2021, the Chairman of the African Union, Cyril Ramaphosa, the President of South Africa, revealed that between April and June, the continent would receive at least 50 million doses. "We as a continent have focused on collaboration and joint action since the beginning of this pandemic. We took the further step to

procure vaccines independently from our own limited resources," Ramaphosa stated (Adepoju, 2021).

While COVID-19 caused over a million lives worldwide by the end of 2020, Africa has prevented a large breakout. African Centers for Disease Controlling and Preventing (CDC) and several nations are collaborating with Civil Society Analysis, Patterson and Balogun (2021) postulate that answers show the kinds of agencies anchored in inappropriate contextual expertise, pan-African solidarity and the lessons learnt from past health crises concerning health messages and community mobilization. However, collaboration has not always been consistent since actors have taken a variety of methods and challenged the use of traditional medicine as COVID-19 treatment through their contact with global public health organizations and civil society partnerships (Patterson & Balogun, 2021).

African CDC Actions shows a collaboration agency, which is anchored in the need for International solidarity and a specific technical response on a continental level and which is based on this recognizable need (Nyabiage 2020). Harmonization is facilitated by developing and investing in specialized and technical knowledge in Regional Institutions such as CDC in Africa and West African Health Organization (WAHO), the specialized health organization of the West African Economic Community (ECOWAS).

Alternatives and Challenges to Multilateralism

The COVID-19 pandemic is a game-changer that raises the question of multilateralism and the current world order. It is a moment to rethink current structures, as well as bilateral and multilateral relations. "At the systemic level, the collapse of the multilateral system would unravel regimes and institutions that are crucial for global stability" (De Wijk, Thompson, Chavannes, 2020, 55). This would lead to a new global power distribution and more complications to solve the existing and arising issues, likewise, nationalism and protectionism would be dominant due to the governments' necessity to protect their countries (De Wijk et al., 2020). At present, the pandemic has also affected the global political systems in aspects like closing borders, weakening all forms of cooperation, and leaving national governments as the main decision-makers regarding COVID-19 measures. Although in many cases the role of the WHO as a multilateral institution has been strengthened as well (Esteves & Van Staden, 2020).

The pandemic stressed the importance of multilateral cooperation which has a lot to do with the basis for peace and prosperity. It is therefore beneficial for countries to cooperate. However, agreeing and supporting multilateralism is not enough, since there are multiple challenges to this, especially with a global threat like COVID-19 and the economic recovery that will be much needed (Le Pere, 2020; De Wijk et al., 2020). In the case of Africa, the pandemic stressed the vulnerability at a time when international cooperation and a more functional multilateral system could permit dealing with the systemic social, health and economic risks and conditions; without the proper measures in Africa as in most countries, the infections and fatalities will escalate. Nonetheless, the multilateral system is facing its own changes (Le Pere, 2020). Evidently, "multilateralism's biggest challenge is to come to terms with global power shifts, zero-sum nationalism, new interstate rivalries, and crises such as the COVID-19 outbreak" (De Wijk et al., 2020, 54).

De Wijk et al. (2020) submits that "there is no Plan B as an alternative for the present multilateral order". In addition, Le Pere (2020) asserts that the Multilateral system should have resilience and be more adaptive to solve the issues raised by COVID-19. In this regard, he

points out some strategies to be included in foreign policies for South Africa -which could be replicated in the whole continent and other regions, such as building regional alliances and mechanisms for cooperation also with non-state actors working through the existing structures and institutions at the Africa and United Nation level to finding better ways to address the pandemic; use multilateral mechanisms for financing the most affected countries' public health systems; and developing vaccine therapies through its medical infrastructure.

Africa has received multilateral support to tackle COVID-19 from International actors like the EU and the World Bank, the latter announced in 2020 that two-thirds of its projects would be addressed to the health sector and about USD 55 billion would be dedicated to fighting the pandemic in Africa. Similarly, other stakeholders from the private sector like the International finance Corporation (IFC) have also provided loans that help to accelerate the COVID-19 responses (Lakemann, Lay & Tafese, 2020). This kind of multilateral cooperation provides the means for African Institutions and banks to find solutions to the threats posed by the pandemic. Aside from financial support, multilateralism also facilitates exchanging knowledge, practices and other resources that contribute to finding joint solutions and thus, remains the best alternative to tackle a global threat like COVID-19.

Conclusion

Stopping the global COVID-19 pandemic requires meaningful International cooperation. Hence, efforts to address the current and future health crises should include greater collaboration among governments in low and middle income to increase their own scientific and technological capacity and produce more equitable access to intellectual property rights and cutting-edge research at the global level. At the same time, efforts in research and vaccination must consider the role of regional organizations as they are known to assist with the dilution to a certain extent of a system of bilateral cooperation that targets strategic cooperation into means of cooperation that are more humanitarian oriented. In addition, wealthier countries and big pharmaceutical companies should agree to a more democratic access to the cures that they fund and produce in cases of international emergency (Paterson, 2021).

The structure and modalities for distribution of the anticipated COVID-19 vaccine, advocate optimum involvement in the community. In order to boost the acceptance of the anticipated vaccination. It is also important to develop feedback mechanisms to recognize community efforts in past health intervention. Moreover, improved cross-sector collaboration to encourage acceptability of COVID-19 vaccinations by supplying additional resources to address the vaccination hesitancy should be launched and promoted. Further integration into the standard immunization schedule of COVID-19 would enhance the medical system and improve the use and health of its vaccines in the whole of Africa (Afolabi & Ilesanmi, 2021).

Whilst countries and organizations have committed themselves to helping developing countries, further efforts are required. A robust cooperation between nations to resolve inequalities in vaccine access can help successfully combat the pandemic. The African continent is therefore vital to help acquire COVID-19 vaccinations through balancing all power dynamics affecting access and distribution. It is also necessary to defend the pan-African aims and that the countries of the continent take responsibility and explore indigenous ideas to regulate COVID-19 in Africa, and maybe Africa will finally pay for Africa (Lucero- Priso et al, 2021).

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